

PADST

Public Administration Capabilities for Digital and Sustainable Transition

D5.3 TALTECH RESEARCH STRATEGY ON FUTURE GOVERNANCE

Project acronym:	PADST
Call:	HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ACCESS-03-01
Grant Agreement:	101079227
Deliverable Lead:	TalTech
Contributing Partners:	KUL, UU, UCL
Submission Date:	31/07/2023
Dissemination Level:	Public
Status:	Version 1.0

Document Information

Deliverable ID:	D5.3
Deliverable Name:	TalTech research strategy on Future Governance
Due Date of Deliverable:	31/12/2023
Actual Submission Date:	31/12/2023
Work Package:	WP5
Lead Organisation for Deliverable:	TalTech
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List of Abbreviations

DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
ER	Experienced Researcher
ESR	Early-Stage Researcher
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
TalTech	Tallinn University of Technology
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Deliverable 5.3 (D5.3)

Based on the education, training and research planning of the project, PADST has developed a concept paper for TalTech's research strategy on Future Governance. This concept paper informs TalTech's future strategic actions around one of its key interdisciplinary research focus themes. Digitalization and sustainability are the core focus of this effort.

Research Strategy on Future Governance

Background

University R&D Context

This deliverable aims to help map the path toward increasing the relevance of research (and teaching) in public administration and governance, establishing TalTech as a knowledge centre in the governance in and of digital and sustainable transition. As TalTech embarks on this journey, the Ragnar Nurkse Department of Innovation and Governance – the key research centre of TalTech in Future Governance – is committed to leading the modernizing of the respective capabilities in research, teaching and knowledge transfer.

Future governance and innovative businesses is one of the research focus areas of TalTech, along with smart and energy-efficient environments, dependable IT solutions, valorisation of natural resources, health technologies, smart maritime sector and sustainable marine environment. The key prerequisite here is to ensure the complementarity of the five research fields.

TalTech defines this research focus area as the R&D “focused on social, technological, economic, regulatory and environmental changes and their leadership to shift towards a more sustainable organisation of society and economic structure both in Estonia and globally”.¹

Field-specific context

In today's dynamic and ever-changing world, public administration needs to adapt and transform into more agile, resilient, and innovative. To effectively address these challenges, the public administration (PA) research agenda needs to sharpen its focus and vision.

The current policy landscape is characterized by many complexities, uncertainties, and rapid technological advancements. Moreover, a prevailing emphasis on short-term gains and a reluctance to embrace risk-taking hinder the ability of PA to effectively navigate these challenges. These complexities are further exacerbated by the looming threat of armed conflicts and hybrid warfare along the borders of the European Union (EU).

The knowledge and policy capacities tend to be divided unequally between different policy fields. Among them are Digital and Green Transitions that require new competencies, capabilities, and governance frameworks.

There are accumulated dynamics affecting the social and economic aspects of sustainability:

- the gap is increasing between the fast-emerging technologies and related institutions that reform at a much slower pace;
 - growing demand for skills and competencies for future governance;
 - the lack of environmental and climate assessment skills is slowing down the pace of climate-related investments in EU municipalities;²

¹ Academic Strategic Plan. Amended by Resolution No 20 of 21.06.2022 of the Council of Tallinn University of Technology. [Academic Strategic Plan - TalTech webportal](#)

² Investment report 2022/2023 – Resilience and renewal in Europe, European Investment Bank, 2023, <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2867/307689>

- increasing disagreement between growth-driven capitalism and the ecological crisis that provides public administrations an entirely new context;
- new armed conflicts, mass displacements, financial crises, pandemics;
- euroscepticism and populism further erode support for the transition towards sustainability.

The urgency of the EU's green and digital policy is yet to translate into new organisational capacities. Dynamic capabilities remain elusive for most innovation bureaucracies. To address this, public organizations must develop long-term capacities³ and professionalise new capabilities for change and stability⁴. This will allow them to navigate the complexities of urgent transitions like the green and digital revolutions amidst deep uncertainty.

Agile innovation practices have shown promise, but scaling and institutionalising these methods face significant challenges. Legacy systems, the need for adaptability, and a risk-averse culture require careful consideration when implementing agile approaches.⁵

The new governance frameworks are called for, and they shall rest on novel public sector capacities that help progress towards sustainable and just pathways while operating in poly-crisis and disruptive pressure on democratic institutions. When the scale and speed of trade-offs are accelerating, societal challenges and well-being must not be pushed on the sidelines. Thus, the key concepts of future governance need to secure various values such as decentralisation, accountability, and democratic participation.

Given that many of these topics have not been studied in depth, future governance researchers should prioritize country-specific and multidisciplinary research projects to generate new knowledge and understanding in these areas. Further studies are needed to explore how public organisations develop capacities and skills (dynamic capabilities, unique, flexible organisational routines)⁶ for maintaining the stability and agility necessary to handle complex urgencies like green and digital transitions in a context of deep uncertainty.

³ Veiko Lember, Rainer Kattel and Piret Tõnurist, 'Technological capacity in the public sector: the case of Estonia', *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 84(2) (2018): 214–30.

⁴ Kattel, R., Drechsler, W. and Karo, E., 2022. *How to make an entrepreneurial state: why innovation needs bureaucracy*. Yale University Press.

⁵ Ines Mergel, 'Agile innovation management in government: a research agenda', *Government Information Quarterly* 33(3) (2016): 516–23.

⁶ Kattel, Rainer and Mariana Mazzucato, 'Mission-oriented innovation policy and dynamic capabilities in the public sector', *Industrial and Corporate Change* 27(5) (2018): 787–801; Teece, David, 'Dynamic capabilities and entrepreneurial management in large organizations: toward a theory of the (entrepreneurial) firm', *European Economic Review* 86 (2016): 202–16; Constance Helfat and Jeffery Martin, 'Dynamic managerial capabilities: review and assessment of managerial impact on strategic change', *Journal of Management* 41 (2015): 1281–1312.

Future Governance Research at TalTech

Informed by the context as described above, the TalTech Future Governance research will be implemented on three levels:

- addressing the Research, Innovation & Development needs of Estonia;
- pan-European and international research agenda coordination and interdisciplinary research in cooperation with other research groups (e.g., environmental, ICT);
- transferring the gained research insights and knowledge by teaching future-proof capacities to national, regional and city administrations (subject to a separate strategy).

The following research agenda summarizes the research streams and actions foreseen in the coming years. Each action will represent a mid or large-scale research effort lasting 3-5 years.

Research Agenda: Future Governance in and of the Digital and Green Transition

Theme 1: Envisioning Future Governance for Sustainable Transition

- Setting up the interdisciplinary Centre of Excellence (CoE) in renovation wave (RW): Led by TalTech built environment, and having partners from TalTech, Tartu and Tallinn universities, the CoE aims to contribute to solving Estonian societal and economic challenges, transforming 75% of existing building-stock with poor energy performance to zero-emission buildings (ZEB) with maximized co-benefits and improved life quality by 2050. The goal is to extend the excellence in ZEB technologies and induce systemic reforms encompassing innovative technologies, novel governance models, novel participatory and collaborative approaches to engage citizens. Among other research questions, the CoE seeks to address (a) which governance models would help to avoid the increase of housing inequalities because of the RW as well as what is (b) the role of sustainable values, sense of personal responsibility formation and trust towards institutions as key factors that would help to secure a widespread and equitable progression of the RW. An auxiliary research action includes the governance of energy communities in Estonia and beyond.
- Setting up the interdisciplinary Centre of Excellence (CoE) in Sustainable Food Systems: Led by TalTech biotech research centre, the CoE strives to take a leading role in Estonia to coordinate and communicate the activities towards food security and sustainability, educate the next generation experts in the field and support the transformation of innovation in food sciences from labs to society. The CoE activities cover various aspects of the food system, ranging from local side-stream upcycling, developments of CO₂ fixing bioprocesses for food applications, microbial valorisation of side streams into alternative proteins, precision breeding for the improvement of crops used in the food industry and development of bio-based alternatives for sustainable, food-grade packaging. The role of TalTech governance research is to study the socio-economic acceptance of sustainable solutions and build governance capacities to support the sustainability transitions of the food systems.
- Monitoring Estonia's Just Transition process: The action builds capacities for Just Transition monitoring of the oil shale and carbon emissions intensive region of Ida-Virumaa in Estonia. The role of TalTech governance research will be to analyse the role and build models to develop further policy and administrative capacities and capabilities in the context of multi-level governance of sustainability transitions. The project includes both academic research streams and targeted capacity-building efforts in Ida-Virumaa.
- Developing alternative technology governance and production systems: COSMOLOCAL

addresses the urgency of localising production amid a systemic crisis by studying “cosmolocal” production — a fusion of digital commons and localised manufacturing. This emerging mode of production involves globally developed design and software commons coupled with local manufacturing technologies and with local biophysical conditions and resources in check. COSMOLOCAL aims to advance the nascent field of cosmolocal production, leveraging a global team of researchers and practitioners. The project comprises three interconnected research streams: technology, sustainability, and institutions for transition. COSMOLOCAL’s novel approach and diverse case studies may contribute to a comprehensive understanding of cosmolocal production’s potential in both the Global North and South, fostering a paradigm shift toward self-sufficient economies.

- Creating a Culture of Twin Transition in Cities: Foster a culture of digital innovation, encouraging experimentation, risk-taking, and continuous learning. Develop mechanisms creating a supportive environment for connecting charismatic champions and institutionalized expert communities.
- Envisioning Sustainable Procurement and Technology Stewardship: Investigate sustainable procurement practices for public innovation purchases, considering factors such as energy efficiency, environmental impact, and ethical sourcing.

Theme 2: Harnessing Innovation and Technology for Inclusive and Equitable Governance

- Agility and Experimentation in Public Sector Innovation: Investigate agile approaches and experimentation techniques for fostering innovation in public administration. Evaluate the effectiveness of prototyping and iterative improvement in driving innovation in public services.
 - Experimentation and innovation: How can governments create an environment that supports experimentation and innovation?
 - Agility and adaptability: How can governments make their processes more flexible and responsive to change?
 - How to democratically anchor experimental governance so that citizens would perceive the experimentalist approaches as legitimate?
- Fostering New Public Administration Capabilities for Sustainable Transition
 - How can governments develop the capacity and capabilities to address sustainability transition and anticipate emerging challenges and opportunities?
 - Upskilling Public Servants for the Twit Transitions Era: Investigate the challenges and opportunities of upskilling public servants in digital literacy, data analytics, and technology-enabled service delivery. Develop strategies for effective training and capacity development programs tailored to the specific needs of green and digital transformations.
- Framing the Data and AI Governance: In cooperation with TalTech Finest Twins Smart City Centre of Excellence, University of Tartu and other centres, explore the role of data technologies in shaping future governance frameworks, addressing twin digital and green transitions. A state-funded flagship data infrastructure IMO, Infotechnological Mobility Observatory (iro.ut.ee) is a key partner and opportunity.
- Implications of digital transformation on Public Administration: Study and advise European governments in shaping responsive, trusted and participatory democratic institutions for the future. Together with a group of international partners, the role of TalTech governance

research groups will be in collaboration with Utrecht University to develop methodologies to analyse the impact of DT on democracy and sustainability issues.

- Navigating the Ethical and Societal Dimensions of Future Governance:
 - Addressing the Ethical and Justice Challenges: Examine the ethical and justice implications of emerging technologies in governance, including biases, fairness, and transparency, and develop frameworks for responsible future governance.
 - Enhancing Social Inclusion and Bridging Digital Divides: Analyse strategies to address the digital divide and promote social inclusion in the context of future governance, ensuring equitable access to digital technologies and opportunities.